

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH BIVALENT METALS.
PART X. TWO MODIFICATIONS OF COPPER
N-DIETHYLBIGUANIDE

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Two varieties of copper N-diethylbiguanide, red and blue-violet, have been prepared, besides a number of salts of the complex base, viz., chloride, hydroxo-chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate and nitrate. From a study of the properties and reactions of the two modifications of the base, they have been represented as *cis-trans* isomers of a planar penetration complex with dsp^2 hybrid bonds. Among the salt of the base, only the chloride has been found to give some indication of occurring in two forms, which, however, could not be isolated in the pure state.

Isomerism in the case of 4-coordinated copper complexes is rather rare. Pfeiffer and Glasser (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, 153, 265) have described two modifications of naphthaldehyde methylimine copper, differing in colour in the solid state. Pfeiffer and Krebs (*ibid.*, 1940, 155, 77) have also reported of two varieties of sodium and barium salts of copper salicylaldehyde phenylimine *p*-sulphonic acid, which differ in their solubility in glycol and glycerine. A definite decision between isomerism and dimorphism could not, however, be made by the authors in these cases. Rây and Chakiabarty (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 609) reported the preparation of two varieties of copper phenylbiguanide and its salts, which were found to differ in their melting point, solubility, and colour in the solid state. The same authors also described three modifications of nickel phenylbiguanide, differing in colour and solubility. Determination of the molecular weight of these copper phenylbiguanides in methyl alcohol proved their monomeric character. It was suggested by the authors that the two copper phenylbiguanides might be viewed as representing *cis* and *trans* isomers of 4-covalent co-ordination complexes, if the possibility of any polymorphism be excluded. Rây and Dutt (*this Journal*, 1948, 25, 63) have also described recently a green modification of copper phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid in addition to the red form, previously reported by Rây and Siddhanta (*this Journal*, 1943, 20, 250).

We have now obtained further evidences in this direction while studying the copper complexes of diethylbiguanide. The copper N-diethylbiguanide has been obtained in two different modifications, rose-red and blue-violet. A 4-covalent complex of substituted biguanide may, however, occur in two different configurations depicted below owing to a difference in the position of valence bonds from the central metal atom :

Hence, a decision between this and the other alternative of *cis-trans* isomerism for the two modifications of copper N-diethylbiguanide under investigation was considered necessary. For this, the following procedure was adopted. It is well known that salicylaldehyde readily combines with ammonia and mono-substituted ammonia to give rise to condensation products like oxyaldimins. These latter, as has been shown by Pfeiffer and co-workers in a series of publications (*Annalen*, 1933, 503, 84; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1937, 149, 217), can co-ordinate with metal atoms to form complexes with configuration as represented below :

Salicylaldimine metal complex.

The same product is obtained when metal salicylaldehyde complex is allowed to react with ammonia or a primary amine :

When copper salicylaldehyde was allowed to react with both the varieties of copper N-diethylbiguanide in methyl alcoholic solution, it led to an immediate separation of a sand coloured crystalline product in each case. The reaction, and the constitution of the product formed, can only be represented as follows :

A binuclear hetero-complex of copper is thus produced. An analysis of the product in each case gave the ratio between copper and nitrogen as 1:5 (approx.). This

indicates that the NH_2 group is free and unco-ordinated in both the varieties of copper N-diethylbiguanide. For, as was already observed, the co-ordinated NH_2 group of an amine, such as that of cobaltic *tris*-ethylenediamine hydroxide, fails to react with salicylaldehyde or copper salicylaldehyde. It can thus be concluded that both the modifications possess the structure (I), as given above. Reaction with mercuric chloride in aqueous solution furnishes confirmatory evidence of the same. Measurement of magnetic moment of the two varieties of the complex base, which give value of 1.65 and 1.68 μ_B , respectively in good agreement with the theoretical value of one unpaired electron, supports the view that the substance belongs to the class of penetration complexes of planar structure with dsp^2 hybrid bonds. We are thus justified in regarding the red and blue-violet modifications of the copper N-diethylbiguanide to be related to each other as *cis-trans* isomers, an assumption of polymorphism being the cause of such strong colour difference in every case of substituted biguanide stands little to reason. In both aqueous and alcoholic solution, however, they practically exhibit the same colour, proving thereby their instability in solution. As the red variety in the solid state is more or less transformed into the blue modification, the latter possibly represents the *trans* configuration.

Among the salts of the complex copper base, only the chloride has been found to give two modifications, one reddish violet and the other blue-violet. The latter could not, however, be obtained in a pure state free from its admixture with the former.

Both the substances are anhydro-bases as represented in structure (I). The blue-violet compound, on heating, is transformed into the red modification at 160°-162° with slight decomposition, and then melts at 198°-200°, the melting point of the pure red variety. They are difficultly soluble in water, and give strongly alkaline solutions. They liberate ammonia from ammonium salts. The blue-violet variety is comparatively more sparingly soluble than the red form. A number of salts, viz. chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate and nitrate of the base was prepared and their properties studied. All the salts decompose slowly in water, and rapidly when heated, with separation of copper oxide, which shows that the strength of the co-ordination and covalent bonds is rather weak, and thereby leads to a rapid hydrolysis of the complex.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diethylbiguanide sulphate was prepared by heating together dicyandiamide (10 g. in 50 c.c. water), diethylamine (40 c.c. of 33% solution) and copper sulphate (13 g. in 50 c.c. water) under pressure on the water-bath with frequent shaking. Copper sulphate solution was added in small portions at a time, fresh amount being introduced as soon as the precipitated copper hydroxide from previous additions dissolved to give a red solution. From the deep red solution finally obtained, a red crystalline product separated out. This was washed with water and dissolved in dilute H_2SO_4 (1:3). Copper was then removed as copper sulphide by H_2S , and the clear filtrate was evaporated to a small bulk on the water-bath. From the concentrated liquor diethylbiguanide sulphate was precipitated in the form of fine crystals by the addition of alcohol. These were washed and dried as usual, yield 14.5 g. (Found: N, 23.76, 23.50; SO_4 , 31.83. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 23.33; SO_4 , 32.0 per cent).

1. *Copper N-Diethylbiguanide.* (a) *Rose-red.*—Copper sulphate crystals (2.5 g.) and N-diethylbiguanide sulphate (6 g.) were dissolved in water (100 c.c.) by heating. A strong solution of ammonia was added to the mixture till the precipitate, first formed, dissolved again giving a deep blue solution. This was filtered, and the filtrate was treated rapidly, drop by drop, with caustic soda solution till the colour of the mixture turned deep red. A rose-red crystalline precipitate separated rapidly. This was immediately collected and washed with cold water, and then dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 and solid KOH; yield 3 g., m. p., $199^\circ\text{-}200^\circ$.

The substance is sparingly soluble in water, but dissolves readily in methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol, as well as in acetone. While kept in contact with water, it slowly changes into the blue-violet form. {Found: N, 37.40; Cu, 16.82, 16.93. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{Big})_2]$ requires N, 37.28; Cu, 16.91 per cent}. Et_2BigH = a molecule of N-diethyl-biguanide, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_6$.

Magnetic susceptibility at 31° : $\chi_g = 2.685 \times 10^{-6}$, $\chi_m = 1008 \times 10^{-6}$, $\chi_A = 1106 \times 10^{-6}$, $\mu_s = 1.65$.

(b) *Blue-violet.*—When the above described rose-red product was allowed to stand overnight in contact with the mother-liquor, it changed into shining bluish violet crystals. These were washed with cold water and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 and KOH. When heated to $160^\circ\text{-}162^\circ$, it changed to the red form, and then melted at $199^\circ\text{-}200^\circ$. It is comparatively less soluble in water than the red form, and like the latter dissolves readily in methyl and ethyl alcohols, as well as in acetone. {Found: N, 36.93, 36.87; Cu, 16.80, 16.85. $[\text{Cu}(\text{EtBig})_2]$ requires N, 37.28; Cu, 16.91 per cent}.

Magnetic susceptibility at 31° : $\chi_g = 2.81 \times 10^{-6}$, $\chi_m = 1055 \times 10^{-6}$, $\chi_A = 1153 \times 10^{-6}$, $\mu_s = 1.68$.

2. *The Complex Chloride.*—The rose-red or blue-violet anhydro-base was treated with a moderately strong solution of ammonium chloride. A current of ammonia gas was then passed into it till a deep blue solution was obtained. This, on heating on the water-bath, or on evaporating in air, gave reddish violet crystals of the chloride. The crystals were washed and dried as usual, m. p. 220° . The product, thus obtained; was found to contain some bluish violet crystals as well. These could be removed by hand picking. {Found: Cl, 15.02; Cu, 13.40; H_2O (by loss at 100°), 5.57. $[\text{Cu}(\text{EtBigH}^+)_2] \text{Cl}_2, 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 14.94; Cu, 13.35; H_2O , 5.61 per cent}.

3. *Hydroxo-chloride.*—The anhydro-base (1 part), red or violet, and ammonium chloride (10 parts) were treated with dilute ammonia to a deep blue solution. A moderately strong solution of caustic soda was added to it, drop by drop, with continuous stirring till the colour of the solution changed to violet. The crystals of the basic chloride then separated from the solution in the form of bright red crystals. These were washed with cold water and dried over CaCl_2 .

The substance is soluble in water and alcohol. In acetone it breaks up into the normal chloride and the base, the latter passing into solution; m. p., 118° . {Found: Cl, 7.95; Cu, 14.26, 14.18. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{OH} \cdot \text{Cl}, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 7.92; Cu, 14.17 per cent}.

Magnetic susceptibility at 31° : $\chi_g = 2.74 \times 10^{-6}$, $\chi_m = 1225 \times 10^{-6}$, $\chi_A = 1373 \times 10^{-6}$, $\mu_s = 1.84$.

The *complex sulphate* was prepared by the addition of ammonia to a solution of copper sulphate (1 mol.) and N-diethylbiguanide sulphate (2 mol.). The rose-coloured precipitate, thus obtained, was washed with water and dried over CaCl_2 . The substance is sparingly soluble in water, but dissolves in strong ammonia to a deep blue solution. In aqueous solution it slowly decomposes with separation of copper oxide. {Found : Cu, 13.43 ; SO_4 , 20.41. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{SO}_4$ requires Cu, 13.41 ; SO_4 , 20.27 per cent }.

A hydrated product was obtained by treating the red or violet base with a solution of ammonium sulphate and ammonia. On allowing the deep-blue solution to evaporate in air, brick-red crystals of the sulphate separated out. {Found : Cu 12.11 ; H_2O (loss at 100°), 10.30. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 12.04 ; H_2O , 10.20 per cent }.

5. The *bromide*, as in the case of the chloride, was prepared from the base, ammonium bromide and ammonia. The substance forms bright pink-coloured crystals, sparingly soluble in water, but readily decomposes in solution with separation of copper oxide ; m. p. 228° . {Found : Br, 29.52 ; Cu, 11.67. $[\text{Cu}(\text{EtBigH}^+)_2]\text{Br}_2$ requires Br, 29.77 ; Cu, 11.81 per cent }.

6. The *iodide* was precipitated as bright pink-coloured crystals when a strong solution of potassium iodide was added to an ammoniacal solution of the complex chloride. It resembles the corresponding bromide in properties ; m. p. 212° . {Found : I, 39.82 ; Cu, 9.98. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{I}_2$ requires I, 40.22 ; Cu, 10.05 per cent }.

7. The *nitrate* was prepared like the complex chloride and bromide, from the base and an ammoniacal solution of ammonium nitrate. It forms reddish violet crystals, sparingly soluble in water, but decomposes in solution with separation of copper oxide. {Found : Cu, 12.65. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{BigH}^+)_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ requires Cu, 12.66 per cent }.

8. *Copper Salicylaldehyde Diethylbiguanide-Copper*.—Copper salicylaldehyde and copper N-diethylbiguanide were dissolved in equimolecular proportions in methyl alcohol. From the clear filtrate the sand-coloured crystals of the compound separated out readily. These were washed with methyl alcohol and dried in air. The substance is soluble in chloroform. {Found : N, 22.33 ; Cu, 19.30. $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)]$ requires N, 21.70 ; Cu, 19.70 per cent }.